

Accultural Processes Of Foreign Students' Adaptation During Study At The University

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 22, 2025</p> <p>Accepted: September 24, 2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Sociocultural Adaptation; Social Networks; Mobile Applications; Academic Mobility</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17194594</p>	<p><i>The process of social and cultural adaptation of foreign students is one of the main factors of their successful study in higher educational institutions of the Russian Federation. In the era of constant technological advancement in the field of acculturation, there is a gap that needs to be explored. The growth in the number of foreign students and the development of Internet technologies are forcing universities to develop new ways of helping students. To study the basic needs of foreign students in this process and, using modern technologies, to create an adaptation program. The number of papers on the topic of various acculturation strategies and methods for their improvement was analysed. The influence of social networks and Internet technologies on the process of sociocultural adaptation of foreign students was studied. Among them, a survey was conducted, which revealed the main problems that emerge during integration into an unfamiliar culture. The survey findings helped to indicate the direction for the development of methods that increase the efficiency of the acculturation process. A project has been developed to help foreign students in creating social ties and their involvement in the culture of Russia. This study indicates that the use of new technologies and resources of the Internet and social networks can become a practical method for the cultural adaptation of foreign students in Russian universities. Further research is necessary to evaluate its effectiveness.</i></p>

Introduction

The globalisation of higher education institutions and the development of educational system in the Russian Federation in accordance with world standards leads to the fact that local universities are becoming more attractive for foreign students. According to the Ministry of Science and Higher Education, in 2019 the number of students in Russian universities was 297.9 thousand people. (The Ministry of Education and Science wants to revise ..., 2019). At the same time, the Kazan Federal University and its branches account for 8,717 foreign students, or 2.9% of the total. An important task for the state and KFU employees is to help foreign students in adaptation. Acculturation is an integral part of adaptation process. It is a difficult stage of transfusion of the individual into a new social and cultural environment and the "adaptation" of the environment to the needs of a particular individual. Foreign students, having individual ethnopsychological characteristics, overcome all kinds of social, verbal, and religious barriers in the process of mastering new types of cognitive and educational activities. Acculturation during the adaptation to a complex of creative factors while studying in a multilingual environment is a gradual and ambiguous process. Specific difficulties are experienced by students studying in a mediator language with the gradual integration of the Russian language without a complex pre-university stage of preparation. The acculturation period for them passes with a significant stress of the compensatory-adaptive systems of the body. As a rule, foreign students go through the main adaptation period at the preparatory stage and in 1-2 years of study. Getting into new socio-cultural conditions, foreign students experience difficulties (of a social, psychological and socio-psychological nature) that affect the success/failure of their intercultural adaptation. Overcoming these difficulties is the task not only of the students themselves, but also of the university teaching staff. The faster a foreign student begins to feel comfortable in a new country and culture, the better the learning process will become.

An important factor in the process of acculturation of students in a constantly changing globalised world is the use of modern technologies and Internet resources. According to statistics, today there are 5.11 billion unique mobile users in the world, while Russians spend up to 7 hours a day on social networks, and this figure will only grow in the future (Digital 2019: global internet ..., 2019). This means that the work of universities with students should also be carried out using social networks, websites and applications. This also applies to the assistance of universities to foreign students. Technology has now become an important part of the interaction between people and practically the primary means of global and interpersonal communication. Mechanisms such as email, social media platforms, instant messengers and various applications provide people

with the ability to connect with family and friends from their native country. Future research on this topic will explore whether technology, the Internet, and the age of social media will influence the overall acculturation experience (Lamar, 2018). Thus, research by scientists from Texas reveals that the use of the above tools can have a positive effect on the acculturation of foreign students. But what matters here is how they use various social networks and sites and with whom they communicate. The purpose of this paper is to study the basic needs of international students in the process of acculturation and the problems they face. Based on the results obtained, using modern technologies, develop methods that will help them adapt to a new culture more easily.

Literature Review

The acculturation processes have been the subject of research by scientists since the beginning of the 20th century. The definition put forward by Redfield et al. (1936) states that acculturation encompasses all forms of change. The author pointed out that these changes can be biological, social, physical, and so on. With regard to psychological acculturation, Ward (Ward and Searle, 1991; Ward and Kennedy, 1993; Ward et al., 2001) identified three main areas of human life that change during the acculturation process and called them the “ABC of Acculturation.” It examines the affective, behavioural and cognitive aspects of the acculturation process, respectively. The ABC, in turn, is appropriately linked to the various theoretical views that dominate the field: a theoretical framework for stress and stress management, an approach to cultural learning, and an orientation towards social identification for acculturation. In recent years, concerns have been raised about the limited emphasis on ontogenetic development in acculturation theories (Sam, 2006).

Since the middle of the 20th century, the problem of adaptation has become a subject of study in the humanities. According to M.I. Vitkovskaya, I.V. Trotsuk, from the point of view of philosophy and sociology, the need for adaptation in a living organism develops during significant changes in some kind of relationship with the environment. And since both the environment and the person are not inalterable, they change, improve, transform, the adaptation process is considered the fundamental basis of the existence of living organisms (Vitkovskaya and Trotsuk, 2004).

According to V. G. Krysko: “acculturation is the process of mutual influence of people with a certain culture, as well as the result of this influence, which consists of the perception of one of the cultures, usually less developed (although opposite influences are also possible), of elements of another culture or the emergence new cultural phenomena”. In the process of acculturation, each person simultaneously solves two major problems: it strives to preserve its cultural identity and is included in a foreign culture. The combination of possible solutions to these problems provides four main strategies for acculturation: assimilation, separation, marginalisation, and integration. According to E.N. Belaya, until recently, assimilation was considered the most acceptable strategy of acculturation. This is a variant of acculturation, when a person fully accepts the values and norms of another culture, while rejecting his own norms and values. However, today the main goal of acculturation is called the integration of interacting cultures, which is an identification with both the old and the new culture, and will contribute to the establishment of a multicultural personality (Belaya, 2008).

Materials and methods

For this study, theoretical methods were chosen, such as theoretical analysis of scientific literature on the topic, comparison and generalisation of scientific papers. A cross-cultural approach was analysed, suggesting the possibility of taking into account the national and culturally specific characteristics of foreign students (Triandis, 1995); a personality-oriented approach that takes into account the psychological characteristics of students (Rubinstein, 1957); an activity-based approach that ensures the active interaction of the individual with the new sociocultural reality (L.S.Vygotsky, 1996; Rubinstein, 1957). The theoretical basis of the research was formed by: the theory of acculturation, the concept of culture shock (Oberg, 1960); results of ethnopsychological research on the study of intercultural adaptation factors (Lebedeva, 1998).

During preparation for the study, the papers of modern scientists on the impact of digital technologies on the acculturation process were analysed. The main ways of using new technologies in the process of social and cultural adaptation of foreign students in different countries were studied. The influence of these technologies on the effectiveness of students' integration into a new environment were analysed. Various options were considered for the inclusion of Internet technologies in the process of acculturation within the educational process and beyond.

Due to the complexity of the subject matter, it should be noted that the theory and practice of determining the specifics of intercultural adaptation of representatives of different cultures is on the way of formation. As a result of this, at the present moment in psychological science there is a lack of a unified approach to the use of diagnostic tools that make it possible to effectively assess various aspects of intercultural adaptation of foreign students. Empirical research in this direction in the future can be used as a basis for creating a set of methods and techniques for studying the adaptation process of foreign students receiving higher education in Russia.

In order to identify the difficulties that foreign students face in the process of acculturation, the authors conducted an open survey among 50 foreign students of 1st and 2nd courses of the Elabuga Institute of Kazan Federal University. Students from the following countries took part in the survey: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan. The percentage of students was distributed as follows: 22% – students who came from Uzbekistan, 22% – students from Turkmenistan, 20% from Tajikistan, another 20% from Kyrgyzstan and 16% of students from Nigeria (Table 1).

Table 1. Number of students who took part in the survey, by country

Country of origin of the surveyed students	Quantity (in numbers)	Quantity (in %)
Uzbekistan	11	22%
Turkmenistan	11	22%
Tajikistan	10	20%
Kyrgyzstan	10	20%
Nigeria	8	16%

The data obtained from the survey was summarised. On its basis was highlighted a direction for the expansion of existing and the development of new methods necessary to help foreign students in social and cultural adaptation. Recommendations were formed for further study of acculturation processes of foreign students in Russia. Based on the studied materials, their analysis and a survey among foreign students, an adaptation plan has been developed at the Elabuga Institute of the Kazan Federal University.

Results

Intercultural adaptation is a complex multifaceted phenomenon that reflects the process of foreign students settling in a new socio-cultural environment. Its successful course is associated with the presence of high motivation among foreign students for leading activities, it involves the development of social norms, cultural values, behavioural patterns of communication partners as representatives of other cultures while maintaining their own cultural uniqueness (Akhtarieva et al., 2019a; Akhtarieva et al., 2019b). The effectiveness of teaching foreign students largely depends on how quickly they can adapt to a new culture under stress and under the pressure of various factors. Acculturation of students usually takes place during the first two years of study at a university. During this time, the student adapts to the peculiarities of a new culture in different spheres: from learning a language and a new information, to expanding social contacts and overcoming psychological difficulties, like finding his place in a country that is not his own. To calculate what components are included in the process of acculturation of foreign students in Russian universities, a survey was conducted among students of the Elabuga Institute of the Kazan Federal University. According to the results of a survey among 50 foreign students, the following problems were identified (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Difficulties that students face in the process of acculturation (in %)

As the survey findings show, one of the main problems of foreign students' acculturation is communication difficulties. This can include ignorance of the language, lack of social contacts, difficulties in communicating with peers at the initial stage of study at the university. Communication difficulties also cause the greatest concerns among foreign students, since they constantly have to interact with representatives of both the host culture and representatives of other cultures: they need to timely execute documentation in the migration services, establish contacts on educational and social issues with other foreign students, university staff, etc. Another barrier to adaptation in a new environment is the difficulty of getting used to foreign culture. It is worth noting that the results obtained are relevant for students from the countries that took part in the study. Cultural differences may not be as great for students from other countries. Based on the survey findings, the authors identified the main components of acculturation, which require careful study and refinement (Fig. 2).

Figure 2.
Components
intercultural

of

adaptation

It is important to note that the adaptation of a foreign student to each of the components should take place simultaneously and evenly. Studying the Russian language for students who come to Russia from other countries is necessary for effective inclusion in the educational process, the formation of a new circle of communication, the study of the culture and traditions inherent in the country and a particular region. On the psychological side, acculturation in a new educational environment can be a negative predictor of quality of life in the context of physical and mental health. Difficult financial situation and problems in the domestic sphere can also prevent a foreign student from quickly adapting to a new environment. For each of the listed components, it is necessary to develop methods that will facilitate the adaptation of students from other countries.

The authors of this study have focused on developing methods for more effective social and cultural adaptation for components "communication, language" and "culture, traditions". In the process of inculturation – the exploitation of foreign culture – a person's spiritual experience expands due to the inclusion of new practices, knowledge, values, and interactions. As a result of this process, the student's social orientations change. This is manifested in the expansion of social ties and overcoming ethnocultural limitations. In the context of inculturation, language acts as a linguistic code of culture, which creates a framework for the formation of a student's national worldview. There are various ways for foreign students to explore a new culture. In this paper, 4 methods are identified: reading literature and watching movies and television programmes; conducting of various events by the university to involve foreign students in the cultural environment of the country; exploring the city where the student lives, the opportunity to visit cultural monuments and sign up for excursions; communication with local students, which helps foreign students not only to study the Russian culture, but also to share about their culture. To find out which of these methods are most effective for students from other countries, a survey was conducted. The findings are presented below (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. What helps foreign students to learn about Russian culture?

The survey findings indicate that the most ineffective way to immerse themselves in Russian culture, according to foreign students, is to study Russian literature, and watch movies and TV broadcasts. One of the reasons for these low rates is the inability to experience real emotional, social and physical experiences while studying literature or movies. According to respondents, the best ways to integrate into a new culture are exploring the city and communicating with local students.

After processing the findings, the authors have developed a primary adaptation program. It must accomplish several tasks:

1. Help foreign students to learn Russian language;
2. Acquaint them with the Russian culture and teach about the history of a city;
3. Acquaint students with vital places of a city (hospitals, migration service, food outlets, etc.);
4. Create the conditions necessary for expanding the range of contacts of foreign students.

To accomplish these tasks, it is important to use modern technology. The process of cross-cultural adaptation can be greatly facilitated by social networks, various sites and applications. Taking these factors into account, the authors of the paper have developed a project that will help foreign students to make the acculturation process faster and more efficient. It was also taken into account that the successful course of this process is associated with the high motivation for leading activities among foreign students.

The objectives of this project include: development of a mobile game application, which will allow students to better navigate the city and study historical and cultural monuments; creating a system of bonuses and motivation for foreign students who participate in university life, demonstrate high academic performance in Russian language, help in organising events.

The concept of the application is to involve students in the gameplay, with the help of which they will study the culture of the city and country, be able to better navigate the area, get to know other students and get an opportunity for psychological relief. In order to reach a new level in the game, students will need to move around the city, solve simple logical problems, memorise new information and speech patterns in Russian, and be creative in the game completion. The application should include the ability to earn bonuses and rewards that can be exchanged for real things – for example, for food in the university canteen. The advantage of this project is the opportunity to interest not only foreign students in the national culture, but also Russian students.

Consider the mechanisms of social and psychological adaptation of the individual (according to F.B. Berezin):

- 1) cognitive, which covers all mental processes related to cognition: memory, thinking, imagination, sensation, perception, etc.;
- 2) emotional, which contains moral feelings and emotional states: excitement, joy, anger, inspiration, happiness, anxiety, etc.;
- 3) practical (behavioural), based on a certain directed human activity.

It is worth noting, that the formulated project will help to set in motion all the listed mechanisms. It can also help foreign students find common ground with students from Russia, create a group of people with common interests. This can be facilitated by creating a community on one of the popular social networks, where students will be able to exchange information about the game, help each other in completing levels, and so on. To evaluate the effectiveness of the project, a test period of at least a month is required. The result of the development and popularisation of the application should be the rapid inclusion of foreign students in all spheres of city life, improvement of work within the educational process and their integration into the Russian culture. Compared to traditional means of social and cultural adaptation, the application will allow the institute to interact directly with foreign students with relatively low resource costs and a high level of efficiency.

Discussion

Foreign students, studying in the Russian Federation, associate their future work with it. They represent an additional reserve of young highly qualified specialists for the Russian economy. Studies indicate that the quality of the learning outcomes of specialists depends on how quickly foreign students can adapt to the social and cultural realities of the country. The most effective way of acculturation, according to the studies of E. N. Belaya and other scientists, is integration. For successful intercultural communication, it is necessary to abandon the perception of someone else's culture through the prism of native culture. It is important for students from different cultures to show tolerance and empathy during communication, to see the value of cultural diversity in the educational environment. Any adaptation programs and methods developed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education or by individual universities should be guided by this method.

According to Schumann's research, foreign students identify language as an important problem in adaptation and social integration (Schumann, 1978). The researcher stated that language is an important indicator of social integration and adaptation. It allows for active communication and exchange of social and cultural identities. Lack of fluency implies problems with adaptation and understanding of culture. Participants of study conducted by M. T. Shayne (Shayne, 2016) emphasised that language is a key and influential factor in their adaptation, engagement, capital acquisition, and social integration. The participants stated that they do not reject their cultural values or cultural identity in order to ensure adaptation and social inclusion. They have changed their attitude towards certain aspects of another culture to accommodate their interaction and social integration. This study defines language learning as not only for improving academic performance, but also for more effective social adaptation. However, it is difficult to name language as the main factor in acculturation, as indicated in previous studies. This is especially relevant for students of Russian universities from the CIS-countries. For them, the main difficulties in communication arise not so much because of the language ignorance, but because of the lack of social contacts and ignorance of the cultural norms of the new country during communication. This study offers ways to solve both the language and communication difficulties.

E. S. Kashima and E. Loh primarily look at the relations between acculturation of international students and the social networks they use in the host society. The social bonds that students develop with other international students from different countries increase the efficiency of acculturation. The more international contacts students develop in a new country, the better they are psychologically. Students with closer international ties also tend to identify more clearly with their native culture and with their university. Hence, connections with other foreign students seem to be important for the development of new identities among foreign students, as well as for their psychological adaptation. (Kashima and Loh, 2006). However, the study does not consider the possibility of uniting foreign students in communities using Internet resources, rather giving them new opportunities for communication with each other within the educational process and beyond. This study examines the possibility of a university to influence the acculturation process using social networks and mobile apps. Since effective communication is essential for cross-cultural adaptation, targeted communication through social media and websites can help accelerate this process. This question was investigated by J. R. Rui and H. Wang. In their opinion, the communication of the university via the Internet can allow people to directly gain knowledge about the culture of the host country, seek help and, therefore, improve their adaptation skills. In other words, directed communication can facilitate cross-cultural adaptation, but using different approaches. (Rui, and Wang, 2015). But the variety of approaches remains unexplored in their study. According to the authors of this paper, the variety of means provided by modern technologies can help not only to speed up the process of social and cultural adaptation, but also improve the performance of foreign students in Russian universities.

Q. Yu, P. Foroudi & S. Gupta in their studies discuss a positive relationship between student performance and the perceived value of their university education. International students who have gained positive experience during their educational process in another country have the best academic performance. Research has shown that academic performance is one of the most important indicators for students, especially foreign ones, in evaluating their foreign educational experience, that is, in shaping the value of the foreign university in which they study. This leads to loyalty to the university. This means that in the future they will be more willing to share their experiences with others and recommend the university. That is, the degree of student

satisfaction with their knowledge affects the prestige of the university. (Yu et al., 2018). It is worth noting, that this paper considers such aspect of acculturation as the study of the language and culture of a new country. According to earlier papers, this can improve the performance of foreign students and their experience in the university. But the use of modern technologies to help in social and cultural adaptation demonstrates the progressiveness of the methods of this university and increases its prestige in the country and in the world.

Researchers from Santiago Ferres and Graells -Garrido experimentally found that the impact of gaming and augmented reality applications on the development of interpersonal communication and city exploration is quite significant. They compared the behaviour of a subgroup of the population before and after the launch of the “Pokémon Go” mobile game app in Santiago. The availability of the game increased the number of people who connected to the Internet on their mobile phones by 13.8% during lunch and 9.6% at night (Graells-Garrido et al., 2017). Further study of the relations between the patterns urban mobility, mobility and interests revealed that the number of people in the city increased. Appeared the groups that explored the city to complete the game. The amount of time that city residents spend outside has also increased. This study examines the possibility of the impact of mobile gaming applications on a narrower audience. The possibility of influencing the acculturation processes of foreign students was not discussed in the early studies. Studying this method can completely change the approach to creating adaptation programs for students. Also, the impact of applications and their discussion on social networks on improving communication between international students and students from the host country should be explored. Comparison with previous studies revealed that the subject of the influence of modern technologies on the process of acculturation is too low. This study can start a chain of researches on this topic.

Conclusion

The study showed that the main problems for foreign students in the process of acculturation are the difficulties in getting used to another culture and the problems with communication. At the same time, foreign students consider the most effective way to integrate into Russian culture is to explore the city with the help of various excursions and communicate with peers from Russia. In their opinion, the least effective way is to read literature and watch movies. Based on this information, the authors of the paper identified methods that can be implemented by the university to help students adapt to a new culture. The authors consider it necessary to study the differences in acculturation processes in students from different cultures. Strategies that work for some students may be less effective for others due to cultural differences.

The adaptation program developed by the Elabuga Institute of the Kazan Federal University, that includes working with social networks and creating a game application to help international students integrate into a new culture, can positively affect their level of adaptation to the country. Further research of this method and a correct evaluation of its effectiveness are required. Also, other areas of interaction between universities and foreign students should be developed with the help of new technologies. The state of knowledge of the impact of university's digital projects for the effective cultural and social adaptation of foreign students is very small. In conclusion, we can add that the involvement of students themselves in the development of such programs can also positively affect the creation of effective methods of foreign students' acculturation in Russian universities.

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